

Location of Trioxygenation Patterns in the A-Ring of Flavones using ^1H NMR

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The ^1H nmr spectra of 5,6,7- and 5,7,8-trimethoxyflavones show that H8 (proton at C8) and H6 resonate in the regions δ 6.67–6.81 and 6.30–6.50 respectively. In 5-acetoxy-6,7-dimethoxy- and 5-acetoxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavones, H8 and H6 absorb around δ 6.82–6.92 and 6.61–6.70 respectively. The H8 and H6 signals are observed around δ 7.20–7.40 and 6.73–6.80 in 5,7-diacetoxy-6-methoxy- and 5,7-diacetoxy-8-methoxyflavones respectively. The ranges for H6 and H8 are δ 6.83–6.96 and 6.67–6.69 in 5,6-diacetoxy-7-methoxy- and 5,8-diacetoxy-7-methoxyflavones respectively. As these ranges are independent of B- and C rings substituents, a distinction between 5,6,7- and 5,7,8-trioxygenation in A-ring can be easily made.

In 1982, an extractive from *Rhamnus virgata* was shown to be 3,5,7,8,4'-pentahydroxyflavone¹ using Gibb's Test² for locating the trioxygenation pattern in A-ring. There are several reports³ for structural changes in naturally occurring flavones and many of these involve revisions from 5,6,7- to 5,7,8-trioxygenation pattern or vice versa. A survey of literature data has, therefore, been undertaken so as to draw a line of distinction between the two types of trioxygenation patterns.

Fig 1. For substituents, see Table 1 (1–96) and the text (97–99).

The δ values for H8 (proton at C8) in 12 flavones (32–43) with 5,6,7-trioxygenation are shown in Table 1. In 3,5,6,7,2',3',4'-heptamethoxyflavone (39), H8 resonates at δ 6.67 and the corresponding value in 5,6,7-trimethoxyflavone (32) is δ 6.84. In the remaining flavones, H8 lies in the region δ 6.68–6.84. The values for H6 in the flavones 87–96 with 5,7,8-trimethoxy substituents are in the range δ 6.30–6.50. In 5-acetoxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavones (1–14), H8 resonates in the region δ 6.82–6.92 (Table 1). In the isomeric 5-acetoxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavones (73–86), H6 absorbs in the range δ 6.61–6.70. The A-ring proton H8 absorbs around δ

7.20–7.40 in 5,7-diacetoxy-6-methoxyflavones (21–27) and H6 around δ 6.73–6.85 in 5,7-diacetoxy-8-methoxyflavones (51–64) as evident from Table 1. The ^1H nmr data for 5,6-diacetoxy-7-methoxy- (15–20) and 5,8-diacetoxy-7-methoxyflavones (65–72) reveal that the ranges for H8 and H6 are δ 6.83–6.96 and 6.67–6.69 respectively (Table 1).

It looks that there is no natural occurrence for 5,6,8-trioxygenated flavones³. The reports with this oxygenation pattern in A-ring have been proved³ to be wrong.

The 6,7,8,-trioxygenated flavones are expected to be distinct because H5, being *peri* to carbonyl, should be downfield than (i) H6 in 5,7,8- and (ii) H8 in 5,6,7-. For naturally occurring 3,6,7,8,4'-penta-methoxyflavone (97)⁴, there does not seem to be any ^1H nmr report till now.

It may be mentioned here that the existing ^1H nmr procedure⁵ for distinguishing between 5,6,7- and 5,7,8-trioxygenation patterns in flavones involves TMS (trimethylsilyl) derivatives.

An extractive⁶ from *Dodonaea viscosa* has been reported to be 3'-(4"-hydroxy-3"-methylbutyl)-5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxyflavone (98) and in the ^1H nmr spectra of its peracetate H8 resonates at δ 6.86 (99). As H8 absorbs around δ 7.20–7.40 in 5,7-diacetoxy-6-methoxyflavones and H6 resonates around δ 6.73–6.80 in 5,7-diacetoxy-8-methoxyflavones (Table 1), there is a deviation from the expected trend in the report⁶.

TABLE 1— ¹ H NMR LITERATURE DATA* FOR H6 OR H8 IN FLAVONES HAVING TRIOXYGENATION IN A-RING					Ref. no.
Compd. no.	OAc	OMe	Other groups	δ	
				H8	
1	5, 2', 5'	3, 6, 7, 4'	—	6.85	7
2	5, 4'	3, 6, 7	—	6.85	8
3	5, 3', 4'	3, 6, 7	—	6.84	9
4	5, 3'	6, 7, 4'	—	6.82	10
5 ^a	3, 5, 4'	6, 7	—	6.92	10
6 ^a	3, 5, 3', 4'	6, 7	—	6.91	10
7 ^a	5, 4'	6, 7	3-O-rha Ac	6.85	10
8 ^a	5, 3', 4'	6, 7	3-O-rha Ac	6.84	11
9	3, 5, 3'	6, 7, 4'	—	6.89	12
10	5, 3', 4'	3, 6, 7	—	6.84	7
11	5	3, 6, 7, 2', 3', 4'	—	6.82	13
12	5	3, 6, 7, 3', 4', 5'	—	6.86	13
13	5, 3', 5'	3, 6, 7, 4'	—	6.86	14
14 ^a	5, 4'	—	6,7-OCH ₂ O 3'-Ac	6.91	
				H8	
15	5, 6	3, 7, 4'	—	6.86	15
16	5, 6, 4'	7	—	6.96	16
17	5, 6, 2', 3'	3, 7, 4'	—	6.80	7
18	5, 6, 2', 5'	3, 7, 4'	—	6.84	7
19	5, 6, 5'	3, 7, 3', 4'	—	6.92	17
20	5, 6	3, 7, 2', 4', 5'	—	6.83	
				H8	
21	5, 7, 4'	3, 6, 3'	—	7.29	18
22	5, 7, 4'	3, 6	—	7.26	19
23	5, 7	6, 3', 4'	—	7.26	20
24	5, 7	3, 6, 4'	—	7.25	21
25 ^b	5, 7, 4'	6	—	7.40	22, 23
26	5, 7	6	—	7.20	24
27	5, 7, 4'	6, 3'	—	7.29	25
				H8	
28	6, 3'	3, 5, 7, 4', 5'	—	6.75	7
29	3, 6, 7, 3', 4'	5	—	6.94	26
30	3, 7	5, 6	—	7.00	27
31 ^c	7	5, 6, 3', 4'	—	7.04	12
				H6	
32	—	5, 6, 7	—	6.84	24
33	—	5, 6, 7, 2', 3', 4', 5'	—	6.75	28
34	—	5, 6, 7, 2', 3', 4', 6'	—	6.75	28
35	—	5, 6, 7, 2', 3', 5', 6'	—	6.74	28
36	—	5, 6, 7, 3', 4', 5'	—	6.81	29
37	—	5, 6, 7, 5'	3', 4'-OCH ₂ O	6.77	30
38	—	5, 6, 7, 3', 4'	—	6.74	14
39	—	3, 5, 6, 7, 2', 3', 4'	—	6.67	7
40	—	3, 5, 6, 7, 4'	—	6.75	13
41	—	5, 6, 7, 3', 4'	3-OH	6.78	31
42	—	3, 5, 6, 7	—	6.75	27
43	—	3, 5, 6, 7, 2', 4', 5'	—	6.71	17
				H6	
44	5, 7, 8	4'	—	6.93	23
45	5, 7, 8, 4'	—	—	6.93	23
46	5, 7, 8	3', 4'	—	6.93	23
47	5, 7, 8, 3', 4'	—	—	6.94	23
48	5, 7, 8	3', 4', 5'	—	6.95	23
49	5, 7, 8, 3, 4', 5'	—	—	6.93	4
50	3, 5, 6, 7, 4'	—	—	6.94	
				H6	
51	3, 5, 7	8, 4'	—	6.78	32
52	3, 5, 7	8, 3, 4'	—	6.78	32
53	3, 5, 7	8, 3', 4', 5'	—	6.82	32
54	3, 5, 7, 4'	8	—	6.75	32
55	3, 5, 7, 4'	8, 3'	—	6.80	32
56	3, 5, 7, 3'	8, 4'	—	6.73	32
57	3, 5, 7, 3', 4'	8	—	6.77	15
58	5, 7	3, 8, 4'	—	6.75	8
59	5, 7, 4'	3, 8, 3'	—	6.85	8
60	5, 7, 4'	3, 8	—	6.80	33
61	5, 7, 3', 4'	3, 8	—	6.81	34
62	5, 7, 4'	3, 8, 3', 5'	—	6.77	34
63	5, 7	3, 8, 3', 4', 5'	—	6.77	35
64	5, 7	3, 8	—	6.73	

(Table 1 contd.)

				H6	
65	5, 8	3, 7	—	6 69	35
66	5, 8	7, 4'	—	6 67	23
67	5, 8, 4'	7	—	6 69	23
68	5, 8	7, 3', 4'	—	6 63	23
69	5, 8, 4'	7, 3'	—	6 69	23
70	5, 8, 3'	7, 4'	—	6 67	23
71	5, 8, 3', 4'	7	—	6 69	23
72	5, 8	7, 3', 4', 5'	—	6 69	23
73	5	7, 8, 3', 4'	—	H6	
74	5, 3'	7, 8, 4'	—	6 67	13
75	5, 4'	7, 8	—	6 69	13
76	3, 5	7, 8, 4'	—	6 71	13
77	5, 3'	3, 7, 8, 4'	—	6 64	34
78	5, 3', 4'	3, 7, 8	—	6 69	33
79	5	3, 7, 8	—	6 61	33
80	5	7, 8	—	6 69	35
81	3, 5	7, 8, 3', 4'	—	6 70	36
82	3, 5	7, 8, 3', 4', 5'	—	6 61	34
83	3, 5, 4'	7, 8	—	6 63	35
84	3, 5, 4'	7, 8, 3'	—	6 64	34
85	3, 5, 3'	7, 8, 4'	—	6 66	34
86	3, 5, 3', 4'	7, 8	—	6 64	34
				6 67	34
87	—	5, 7, 8, 2', 3', 5', 6'	—	H6	
88	—	5, 7, 8, 2', 3', 4', 6'	—	6 50	28
89	—	3, 5, 7, 8	3', 4'-OCH ₂ O	6 46	28
90	—	5, 7, 8, 3', 4'	—	6 41	37
91	—	4', 5, 7, 8	3-OH	6 46	13
92	—	3, 5, 7, 8, 3', 4'	—	6 40	38
93	—	3, 5, 7, 8, 3', 4', 5'	—	6 40	39
94 ^a	—	5, 7, 8, 2'	—	6 30	39
95	—	5, 7, 8	—	6 44	40
96	—	3, 5, 7, 8	—	6 45	36
				6 41	41

*The solvent is CDCl₃, unless otherwise specified^aIn DMSO-d₆^bThe former structure²² has been proposed²³ to be revised as structure 25^cMean δ value^dIn the synthetic sample 94⁴⁰, δ values for H3 and H6 are shown as 6 44 and 7 00 respectively

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